

EMPOWERMENT THE HALAL INDUSTRY THROUGH CASH WAQF FUND AND ZAKAT

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Abstract

Indonesia is a country which has a lot of Muslim population as much as 87 percent. These conditions make Islamic finance industry is required to provide halal financing access to the businessmen, but the financial institutions such as sharia and conventional banks are unable to provide the funding to businessmen in Indonesia which dominated by Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). On the other hand, there are some public sources of Islamic public fund potentially to be developed such as cash waqf fund that reached Rp. 3 trillion and zakat that reached 200 trillion. This research aims to optimize the role of Islamic public funds such as cash waqf fund and zakat through using the financial technology platform, particularly in crowdfunding platform in order to provide the funding to the businessman in halal industry. The development of financial technology is to create a website named ayoberdonasi.com which can be the alternative solution for SMEs in the halal industry to get the funding, and also can be the marketplace for the businessman. This research is the library research and data processing technique used in the descriptive analysis. The implementation of ayoberdonasi.com is to integrate the management of waqf and zakat in one platform.

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1. Introduction

Indonesia is a country with a diversity of cultures, languages, and religions with a total population over about 240 million people. Although not classified as an Islamic State, but 87 percent of the population of Indonesia are Muslims [1]. The high number of Muslim societies makes Indonesia has great potential in the development of Islamic public funds such as zakat, waqf infaq, and shodaqoh. One of the Islamic public funds that potential to be developed is the zakat funds. Zakat is one of the Islamic public funds that could be used as a strategy for alleviating poverty, unemployment and the increasing degree of life if the allocation of its funds is professionally and productively. Based on table 1 above, it shows that the funds of zakat, infaq and shodaqoh (ZIS) that managed by Badan Amil Zakat Nasional (BAZNAS) has a pretty good trend that is increasing each year [2]. Plus, according to [3] mention that the funds which managed by BAZNAS and Amil Zakat (LAZ) in the year 2017 reached Rp 2.5 trillion. Despite the increase trend number of collecting the zakat funds from the year 2015 until 2017, the numbers are still very low or just 1.2 percent from the potential of its compilation which reached Rp 217 trillion.

In addition, there are other Islamic public funds that potential to be utilized for the welfare of the community which called the cash waqf fund. The waqf is one of the Islamic public funds has an advantage compared to other Islamic public funds because the distribution of the funds can be allocated to anyone and allow its benefits continue until the end of time. The cash waqf fund cash is one example of a fund that has an important role to empower the real sector and strengthen the economy of a country. The cash waqf fund assets in Indonesia according to Agency Waqf of Indonesia (BWI) stated that per December 2013 the cash waqf fund reached Rp 145.8 billion. The

numbers are still low when compared with the potential for collecting the funds that reached Rp 123 trillion per year. The potential is assumed if the 100 million Muslim citizens willing to donate their money amounting to Rp 100 thousand per month [4].

Table 1. Number of collecting the ZIS in Indonesia (2010-2015).

Year	Rupiah (billion)	USD (million)	Growth (%)	Growth of GDP (%)
2010	1.500	109,17	25,00	6,1
2011	1.729	125,84	15,30	6,5
2012	2.200	160,12	27,24	6,23
2013	2.700	196,51	22,73	5,78
2014	3.300	240,17	22,22	5,02
2015	3.700	269,29	21,21	4,79

On the other hand, [5] shows that the management of zakat is not optimize yet, and the research conduct by [6] shows that the management of cash waqf fund same as zakat which not empower the businessman especially in the sector of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). The potential amount of Islamic social funds should be used to empower SMEs sector in Indonesia because SMEs sector has an important role as the driving actor of economic growth. In the year 2015, the number of SMEs in Indonesia is estimated about 60.7 million units and is largely a micro-scale (98.73%). In the same period, the capacity of SMEs to absorb the labor is amounting to 5.9 percent. In the year 2015, the number of labor SMEs reached over 132.3 million [7].

The development of the halal industry in Indonesia can be counted by seeing the owner number of halal certification. According to the Director of the Institute for the study of food, drugs, and cosmetics Majelis Ulama Indonesia (LPPOM MUI) namely IR. Lukmanul Hakim, [M.Si in food.detik.com](http://M.Si.in.food.detik.com) said that in the year 2014 MUI Halal Certificate has published as much as 13,136 certificate for 155,774 food products, drugs and cosmetics, and the product that have owned the halal certification in Indonesia amounted to 59.01 percent that refers to the data products are listed on the POM [8]. That number indirectly describe that businessmen who create the products that have been listed as a halal product is included in the halal industry.

Support is required from the various stakeholders in order to accelerate Indonesia as a central halal industry of the world. Become a central halal industry can be happened if start to empower the SMEs in Indonesia. One of the factor that impede the development of SMEs is access to get the funding, but sharia and conventional bank cannot provide the funding because SMEs is not bankable enough. Therefore, Ayoberdonasi.com can become the solution for SMEs to get the funding. Ayoberdonasi.com is the website that has the function to collect zakat and cash waqf funds using financial technology-based crowdfunding platform. The role of the ayoberdonasi.com as a platform is not only to collect the funds but also able to show the profile of the businessman that will be empowered by the donator. The website of ayoberdonasi.com is a form of centralised collecting the Islamic public funds which managed by BWI and BAZNAS.

1.2 Problem Identification

The problems that will be discussed in this paper are:

1. How does the mechanism in management of zakat and cash waqf funds for the development of the halal industry in Indonesia?
2. Why is there any urgency of the development of the halal industry using Islamic social funds through the website of ayoberdonasi.com?

2. Theoretical Review

2.1 Small and Medium Entreprises (SMEs)

Small and Medium Entreprises (SMEs) is a sector that has a big contribution to Indonesia's economy. Characteristics of SMEs according to the World Bank that cited from [9] shows that the SMEs are grouped into three types, namely; 1) micro enterprise (have 10 people of employees); 2) small enterprise (have 30 people of employees); and 3) Medium Business (have up to 300 people of employees). Based on Act No. 20 Year 2008 explained that the SMEs is a small company that owned and managed by someone or owned by a small group of people with a certain amount of wealth and income.

3.2 The Potential of Halal Industry

Report of the Pew Research Center's Forum on Religion and Public Life in 2017 shows that the number of the world's Muslim population in 2015 is reached 1.8 billion (24.1 per cent of the world population) and is expected to grow to 3 billion by 2060 or about 31 percent of the total population of the world [10]. The Muslim population is business opportunities for halal products. Recently the halal consumer products are not only from Muslims, but also from among the non-Muslims who want to start a healthy life. Thus, it can be predicted that the consumer of the halal products in the world is getting bigger and make any chances to getting high.

The business potential of the halal industry in a very large world should be utilized by Indonesia to become the leader in trading of halal products. Based on the report of the Global Islamic Economy Report 2016/2017 obtained that value food shopping and lifestyle (food and lifestyle sector expenditure) Muslim world halal sector reach US \$1.9 trillion in 2015 and is expected to rise to US \$ 3 trillion in 2021 [11]. It indicates that the development of the halal industry is very rapidly, and it has a great potential to be developed.

3.3 Zakat Fund

According to the compilation of laws on the management of zakat number 38 of 1999, zakat is a treasure that must be set aside by a Muslim or a body owned by the Muslim religion according to the provisions to be given to the right to receive it [12]. Every citizen of Indonesia which categorized as a Muslim and capable enough or agency that owned by Muslims were obliged to fulfil zakat while the Government obligation is to provide the protection, guidance and services to *muzakki* (person or entity that obligation to fulfil zakat), *mustahik* (person or entity that is entitled to receive zakat) and *amil zakat*.

The law number No. 23 of 2011 mentioned in article 1 paragraph 1 that the management of zakat is the activity of planning, implementation, and organizing in the collection, distribution and utilization of zakat [13]. Steps concrete manifestation of zakat funds management carried out by the Government that is by forming a national agency of *amil zakat* (BAZNAS). Then the government formed the institution of *amil zakat* (LAZ) that serves to help collecting activity from the community.

3.4 Cash Waqf Funds

According to a compilation of Islamic law article 1 shows that the waqf is a legal person or a group of persons or legal entities that separates most of his property for the purpose of worship or public use more in accordance with Islamic teachings [14]. According to law No. 41 of 2004

Concerning Waqf property, Waqf are invested only for five kinds of things, namely 1) facilities and worship activities; 2) facilities and activities of education and health; 3) aid to the poor, orphans, abandoned children and orphans; 4) scholarships and other public welfare advancement does not conflict with Sharia and; 5) legislation [15].

The agency Waqf of Indonesia (BWI) is the embodiment of the mandate outlined in Act No. 41 of 2004. The presence of the BWI, as described in article 47, is to promote and develop waqf allocation in Indonesia. For the first time, the membership of BWI was appointed by the President of the Republic of Indonesia, in accordance with the Presidential Decree No. 75/M year 2007, which is set in Jakarta, July 13, 2007. Thus, BWI is an independent institution to develop waqf allocation in Indonesia that in carrying out its duties are free from the influence of any power, as well as accountable to the community.

3.5 Crowdfunding

Crowdfunding is a way that allows for a company or a non-profit organization to collect funds in online platform to be used as a donation or business investment [16]. Crowdfunding in concept is not new, even if the crowdfunding scheme said new, probably it happen because of the development of technology and mindset that gave momentum in chronological order of events, so that the old concept of developing and named with the term a new crowdfunding.

Attention, trust, cooperation, and collective gathering money along with four important aspects in doing Crowdfunding. These four aspects are inter-related and could not be separated from each other. In attention, the owner of the project doing the 'campaign' in order that the owner of the site and the community gives attention to the projects. After the owner of the site and the community provide attention, arising belief instilled by the site owners and the public to the project owner, to do joint Crowdfunding.

3. Research Method

The object in this research is the Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in halal industry. The research was conducted using a qualitative approach. Leksono (2013), explained that the research is qualitative research, and it cannot be resolved through statistical procedures as well as quantitative research. This study uses secondary data types. According to Sanusi (2011), secondary data is data that is already available and collected by other parties. This research uses data obtained from either scientific journals and also in the form of literature that are relevant to the topic of the issue.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1 Mechanism in management of zakat and cash waqf fund for the development of the halal industry in Indonesia

The management of zakat and cash waqf fund should have managed well because Indonesia has big potential to allocate the Islamic social funds to the productive sectors that need to be empowered such as the halal industry sector. Innovative solutions in management of cash waqf funds to empower the halal industry is through the utilization of the agency waqf of Indonesia (BWI) and the national agency of amil zakat (BAZNAS) to do online fundraising using crowdfunding platform in the website named ayoberdonasi.com.

The website of ayoberdonasi.com is useful as one of online fundraising platform that is intended to make it easier for people who want to donate funds. The object of the empowerment using zakat and cash waqf fund is businessmen which categorized as SMEs that has a halal

product and has halal certification. The donator can find out the conditions and the needs of businessmen before deciding to donate. Then the BWI and BAZNAS will do the empowerment to the businessman and help SMEs to report their business development on the website of ayoberdonasi.com to provide the transparency to the donators.

Figure 1. Management Scheme of zakat and cash waqf funds through Crowdfunding Platform

Source: writer analysis

From the figure 1 above, the management of zakat and cash waqf Fund to empower the halal industry in Indonesia which centralized on the website of ayoberdonasi.com can be described as follows:

1. Distribution of cash waqf fund by waqif to *nazhir* (BWI) and the distribution of zakat fund to amil (BAZNAS) is using the role of the ayoberdonasi.com based crowdfunding system. ayoberdonasi.com is the central of online fundraising platform which collect zakat and cash waqf fund.
2. The community that donate their money in the form of cash waqf fund will be directly managed by the BWI, whereas the community that donate their money in the form of zakat will be managed by BAZNAS. The function of the ayoberdonasi.com is to facilitate the community with one website of fundraising so there is no need to access many websites.
3. BWI and BAZNAS will form a special team that will manage the website ayoberdonasi.com and the team that will conduct the mentoring to small-scale businessmen.
4. After get mentoring from BWI or BAZNAS then businessmen were obliged to report business progress and report the financial condition to ayoberdonasi.com every single month as proofing of transparency to the donators. ayoberdonasi.com also serves as a media marketing of products that made by the businessman.

4.2 The urgency of the development of the halal industry using Islamic social funds through the website of ayoberdonasi.com

The development of the halal industry market so rapidly in the world has been stealing the attention of the government and businessmen in many countries. Not just Muslim countries but also countries with a population of non-Muslim majority. The increasing interest people of the world to consume halal products, not just driven by the motivation of belief, but also because of the quality of the product is halal which is indeed the better and healthy. Indonesia is the country with the largest Muslim population in the world has a very big opportunity to become the center of world halal economy. Indonesia also has many halal sectors which very potential to be developed as a food-drink, fashion, financial services, and tourism.

Nevertheless, based on the report of the Global Islamic Economy Report in 2016/2017, it can be noted that Islamic economic indicator scores of Indonesia is reached 10th rank, far behind from other countries. One way to improve the competitiveness of Indonesia's halal industry is improve the productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) sector in terms of financing as well as business development. Because of Islamic finance institutions such as the Islamic bank cannot provide the access to the financing for the SMEs so that another funding source is needed to be able to overcome these problems faced by businessman.

Indonesia is the country that most of the community are Muslim or 87 percent making Indonesia has great potential in the development of Islamic public funds such as zakat and cash waqf fund. The cash waqf fund assets in Indonesia according to the agency waqf of Indonesia (BWI) in December 2013 reached Rp 145.8 billion. The numbers are still very small when compared to the potential of its compilation which is Rp 123 trillion per year. In addition, acceptance of zakat in Indonesia also can still low or 1.2 percent or around Rp 2.6 trillion, whereas the potential of its compilation is amounting to Rp 217 trillion (antaranews.com). So it can be inferred that zakat and cash waqf funds has a great potential to be utilized.

Great potential in the development of the cash waqf funds apparently still not optimally advance for productive activities as described in the research conduct by Djalaludin (2013), Mughnisani (2015), and Ali (2017) that the management of cash waqf funds is still traditional which allocate for the development of vocational education and the granting of scholarships the students. In addition, research conducted by Basri (2013) shows that the management of the zakat fund is still traditional which is distributed in the form of rice or cash.

Rapid technological development and the high number of internet users making online fundraising of zakat and cash waqf fund are effective to be conduct. According to the Internet service provider Association of Indonesia (APJII) in 2016 stated that the number of internet users in Indonesia reached 132.7 million or equivalent to 51.7 percent against 256.2 million populaiton. In addition, if we see at the level of generosity (rate of giving) in Indonesia, based on a survey conducted by the Charities Aid Foundation (CAF) World Giving Index in 2016 indicate that Indonesia reached 7th rank as the most generous countries in the world or reached 56 percent. It shows that zakat and cash waqf fund could potentially to become an option for the people who want to donate their money.

5. Conclusion and Suggestion

5.1 Conclusion

The rapid development of the halal industry gives hope to Indonesia to become the market leader. Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) sector as the main economic driving actor of Indonesia have not been able to compete in the market because it is hampered by funding problems. Through the website ayoberdonasi.com makes businessmen especially in halal Industry can get answers to face the problems that encountered include:

1. The mechanism run by the website ayoberdonasi.com is a form of efficiency of management of Islamic public funds because the system is centralized. The businessmen are facilitated to get the funding directly from the donator who see his profile on a web page. In addition, the SMEs may also sell its products to the website of ayoberdonasi.com.
2. Utilization of financial technology allows SMEs in Indonesia are able to get help from the government or donators to support its business productivity.

5.2 Suggestion

The application of ayoberdonasi.com website requires the coordination of cross-cutting from a range of parties in order to maximize its role. Governments need to make regulation in order to centralizing which collecting zakat and cash waqf fund only can be conduct by the agency waqf of Indonesia (BWI) and the national agency of amil zakat (BAZNAS). Then the Government will also need to expand internet network up to the village in order to be able to reach the community in every region in Indonesia. In addition, academics as well as practitioners should still continue to examine concerning the centralization of fundraising zakat and cash waqf funds to the productive sector to maximize local development to national. Then for the next research, try to analyse the effectiveness of centralised zakat and cash waqf funds based crowdfunding platform.

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